

**A STUDY ON WORK LIFE BALANCE AMONG EMPLOYEES WORKING
WITH ITES INDUSTRY WITH REFERENCE TO BANGLADESH**

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Abstract:

Work life balance is one of the most challenging issues being faced by the employees in the 21st century because of the type of roles they play at home and the spillover of personal life over work life. Consequences of good Work-Life Balance benefit the organization in a variety of ways as improved performance, increased productivity, augmented employees satisfaction and happiness, sound well-being, enhanced organizational image, improved employee retention, reduced cost, reduced stress and improved quality of life and so on. Likewise, the consequences of poor WLB can be a low level of morale and motivation, increased number of grievances, work-family conflict, productivity level, poor organizational image, poor quality of work life, poor quality of life and so on. The main objective of the study is to analyze the factors that influence Work-Life Balance and its Outcomes and to analyze the Work-Life Balance among the Employees across their demographic characteristics. For this purpose a sample of 116 was collected from employees of the companies with ITEs industry in Bangladesh and statistical tools were used to analyse the data and the conclusion is that the companies should take care of employees work load to balance the work life. Organization should consider every individual is unique and precious and should give time for their own personal needs. Increment should be given to the employees for balancing their work life. The organization should increase work life balance programs to reduce company work conflict.

Key Words: Work Life, Work Conflict and Productivity Level

Introduction:

Employees in the present time prefer job between that entail the content of flexibility. Working people including dual career couples require availability of time at different points in different stages of their career to meet different personal and social needs. Resultantly, working people struggle to strike balance between working hours and personal obligations. Organizations in abroad appear to quite alarmed about Work-Life Balance, organizations in India have started realizing the urgency of the need of Work-Life Balance and taking the needed steps. Consequences of good Work-Life Balance benefit the organization in a variety of ways as improved performance, increased productivity, augmented employees satisfaction and happiness, sound well-being, enhanced organizational image, improved employee retention, reduced cost, reduced stress and improved quality of life and so on.

Work-Life Balance does not mean an equal balance. It means the capacity to schedule the hours of professional and personal life so as to lead a healthy and peaceful life. It is not a new concept. It emphasizes the values, attitudes and beliefs of regarding their age to work in organizing and balancing their work and personal life. When a woman achieves a successful work-life balance, she has job satisfaction and becomes highly committed and productive and succeeds in her career. But, in certain cases she is not able to succeed due to incapability in balancing her work and personal life. She is unable to set her priorities. As a result she withdraws from her work due to simple reasons like taking care of her children, aged in laws/parents, and other family pressures. If the man is able to share some of her responsibilities, she would be successful. A survey in the UK reveals that the majority of the has had successful WLB, because their husbands shared an equal partnership both in professional and personal life. With the advancement in technology, and education and revolution in the industrial sector, there has been a little change in Indian men too. Both the partners need to schedule their working hours and personal hours so that they lead a professionally and personally healthy life. The should also educate her children to share responsibilities to make life better and fruitful. are often made in the area of home and family.

Supportive Strategies:

Most of the employees require multiple supports and strategies they use to assist them achieve a healthy work-life balance. The use of time management strategies and the presence of social support from family, friends and neighbors are possible supports in enabling them to manage the demands of their various roles.

Social Support:

Social support can be bifurcated into two facets such as organizational support and family related support. Work related social support comes from the organizational members, such as peers and supervisors, where an employee works, whereas personal social support comes from spouse, parents, children, extended family or friends. Social support is believed to have a positive impact on the working roles performed by at work places by enhancing job satisfaction and creating balance, thereby eliminating work-family conflicts. It is one of the important resources for working to manage their work and family domains. It helps to balance their work and family roles in a positive way by sharing the thoughts and the problems arising out of work and personal affairs

Statement of Problem:

Working conditions, number of days of work, balance all the needs with income, long working hours, worry about work, stress arising from work, feel pressured by many work demands, sexual harassment, travel and satisfy their boss attitudes. Even with home the employees may have a problem towards marital relationship, a hindrance to carry out the responsibilities, Domestic responsibilities, suspicion from family members, Husbands attitude and non co-operations, Attitude of family members, Quality time with family. The main problem of the study is that whether the employees working with ITEs industry are managing their work life balance?

Objective of the Study:

- To study the demographic profile of the respondents
- To assess the level of work life balance of the respondents towards job satisfaction.
- To analyze the influence of demographic variables on work life balance of the respondents towards job satisfaction.
- To suggest suitable measures to enhance work life balance of the respondents.

Scope of the Study:

In research the scope of the study refers to the parameters in which the study will be operating in. In which it reminds the researcher, that the method of investigation should be centered on trying to solve the problem within the provided scope. The scope of this survey would include.

- Helping researcher to analyze the demographic factors affecting the work life balance towards job satisfaction
- This study helps to find out the level of work life balance.
- This study helps to identify the level of Job satisfaction in the organization regarding the factors that contributes work life balance.

The study is helpful to the organization to conduct further research topic and gives an idea about the prevailing working conditions and how to balance their work life. The organization can identify the effects of work life on the success of the organization and guides the company to take better decision in order to balance their work life of the employee.

Limitation:

- The present study examines it from identified and selected dimension only.
- It was difficult to collect the information within a short duration of time.
- This study is applicable only for ITEs industry in Bangladesh.
- This study is purely based on the opinion of the employee which may change in the further.

Need of the Study:

Work life balance is about people having a measure of control over the work. It is achieved when an individual's right to a fulfilled life inside and outside paid work is accepted and respected as the norm, to the mutual benefit of the individual, business and society. Work-life balance is about creating and maintaining supportive and healthy work environments, which will enable employees to have balance between work and personal responsibilities and thus strengthen employee loyalty and productivity. This motivated the researcher to undertake the research. The study is based on the work life balance at the company. The time frame of the study is limited to 6 weeks. The study is undertaken to identify various causes for stress level and imbalance work life at work.

Research Methodology:

Research Design: Descriptive Research design is used for this study.

Source of Data: The task of data collection begins after a research design has been planned out. The primary data are those which are collected a fresh and for the first time, and thus happen to be original in character. The secondary data are those which have already existing collected data by some other else and which have already have been passed through the statistical process.

Primary Data: The primary data was collected using a structured questionnaire from the employees of the ITES Companies.

Secondary Data: Secondary data are collected from the company's manuals, websites, journals, and from library.

Sample Size: The sample size is an important feature of any research in which the goal is to make inferences about a population from a sample. 116 respondents were taken for the collection of data.

Sample Design: A sample design is a definite plan for obtaining a sample from a given population. Simple random sampling was used to select the random samples from the total population.

Scaling Technique: Scaling techniques used in the survey ,for understanding the relation and importance of work life balance towards job satisfaction and the respondents are elucidated by asking them to indicate their level of argument on a given five point like scale with values ranking from “1”(strongly disagree) to “5” (strongly agree).

Statistical Tools Used:

- Percentage analysis
- Mean score value
- Anova

Analysis and Interpretation:

Age:

	Frequency	Percent
Below 30 years	61	52.6
31 - 40 years	31	26.7
41 - 50 years	12	10.3
Above 50 years	12	10.3
Total	116	100.0

Interpretation:

The above table shows about the age of the respondents were out of 116 respondents 52.6% are from the age group of below 30, 26.7% are from the age group of 31-40, 10.3% are form the age group of 41-50, 10.3% are form the age group of above 50. It shows that most of the respondents are from the age group of below 30 years.

Type of Family:

	Frequency	Percent
Joint	3	2.6
Nuclear	113	97.4
Total	116	100.0

Interpretation:

The above table shows about type of family of the respondents were out of 116 respondents 2.6% are from joint family, 97.4% are from nuclear family. It shows that most of the respondents are from nuclear family.

Educational Qualification:

	Frequency	Percent
Higher Secondary	8	6.9
Under Graduate	36	31.0
Post Graduate	62	53.4
Professional	10	8.6
Total	116	100.0

Interpretation:

The above table shows about educational Qualification of the respondents were out of 116 respondents 6.9% are from higher secondary, 31% are under graduates, 53.4% are post graduates and 8.6% are professionals. It shows that most of the respondents are post graduates in our survey.

Occupation:

	Frequency	Percent
Private employee	7	6.0
Government employee	62	53.4
Business	34	29.3
Others	13	11.2
Total	116	100.0

Interpretation:

The above table shows about occupation of the respondents were out of 116 respondents 6% are private employees, 53.4%. It shows that most of the respondents are post graduates in our survey.

Descriptive Statistics for Work Interference with Personal Life:

Descriptive Statistics			
	N	Mean	SD
Level of acceptance towards personal life	116	2.44	1.113
Level of acceptance towards difficulty in personal life because of job	116	3.28	1.454
Level of acceptance towards neglecting personal needs	116	3.03	1.087
Level of acceptance towards putting personal life on hold for work	116	2.61	1.070
Level of acceptance towards personal activities because of work	116	2.95	1.215
Level of acceptance towards juggle work and non-work	116	2.83	1.121
Level of acceptance towards amount of time for non-work activities	116	2.65	.877
Valid N (list wise)	116		

Interpretation:

The above table shows about descriptive statistics for work interference with personal life were the five scaling point strongly agree (1)-strongly disagree (5) was used and mean value less than 3 shows that the respondents suffer out work interface with personal life. It reveals that the mean value for level of acceptance towards personal life is at 2.44, level of acceptance towards difficulty in personal life because of job (3.28), level of acceptance towards neglecting personal needs (3.03), level of acceptance towards putting personal life on hold for work (2.61), level of acceptance towards personal activities because of work (2.83), level of acceptance towards amount of time for non-work activities (2.65).

It shows that their personal life suffers because of work, they put personal life on hold for work, they miss their personal activities because of work, they struggle to juggle work and non-work, they are happy with the amount of time for non-work activities.

The suggestion is that the employees can as what the company itself is doing to contribute to stress on that employee, and see what steps they can take to alleviate it and that might be a matter of changing work volume.

The employees can speak to friends or care workers, who may have an understanding of the situation and be able to take steps quickly to improve the situation.

When employees feel a greater sense of control and ownership over their own lives, they tend to have better relationships with management and are able to leave work issues at work and home issues at home.

Descriptive Statistics for Personal Life Interference with Work:

Descriptive Statistics			
	N	Mean	SD
Level of acceptance towards energy for work	116	2.70	.998
Level of acceptance towards effectiveness at work	116	2.97	1.149
Level of acceptance towards suffering because of personal life	116	2.92	1.073
Level of acceptance towards find it hard to work because of personal matters	116	2.58	.815
Valid N (list wise)	116		

Interpretation:

The above table shows about descriptive statistics for personal life interference with work were the five scaling point strongly agree (1) strongly disagree (5) was used and mean value less than 3 shows that the respondents suffer out of personal life interface with personal work. It shows that the mean value for level of acceptance towards energy for work (2.70), level of acceptance towards effectiveness at work (2.97), level of acceptance towards suffering because of personal life (2.92) and level of acceptance towards find it hard to work because of personal matters (2.58) are less than 3 which shows that remedy measures has to be taken by the company on the factors.

For this the employees can try to use work as a distraction from what is happening at home by really getting stuck into the tasks they have.

Comparison Between Age and Dimensions Used for Work Life Balance With Employees:

- H1: There is no significant relationship between age and work interference with personal life
- H2: There is no significant relationship between age and personal life interference with work
- H3: There is no significant relationship between age and work personal life enhancement
- H4: There is no significant relationship between age and level of acceptance on work life balance
- H5: There is no significant relationship between age and job satisfaction
- H6: There is no significant relationship between age and attributes of job satisfaction

		N	Mean	SD	F	Sig
Work interference with personal life	Below 30 years	61	2.5821	.57411	6.012	0.001
	31 - 40 years	31	2.9723	.88362		
	41 - 50 years	12	3.0858	.68218		
	Above 50 years	12	3.3342	.47950		
	Total	116	2.8163	.71649		
Personal life interference with	Below 30 years	61	2.7008	.66743	2.039	0.113
	31 - 40 years	31	2.7661	.61215		

work	41 - 50 years	12	3.1042	.63477		
	Above 50 years	12	3.0417	.46262		
	Total	116	2.7953	.64065		
Work personal life enhancement	Below 30 years	61	2.7295	.65875	3.744	0.013
	31 - 40 years	31	2.8629	.55842		
	41 - 50 years	12	3.1042	.69461		
	Above 50 years	12	3.3542	.73437		
	Total	116	2.8685	.66795		
Level of acceptance on work life balance	Below 30 years	61	2.9164	.57942	3.916	0.011
	31 - 40 years	31	3.1194	.51473		
	41 - 50 years	12	3.3583	.55671		
	Above 50 years	12	3.3667	.47354		
	Total	116	3.0629	.57127		
Job satisfaction	Below 30 years	61	3.0836	.71465	.793	0.500
	31 - 40 years	31	3.0419	.43572		
	41 - 50 years	12	3.3333	.66652		
	Above 50 years	12	3.2333	.62134		
	Total	116	3.1138	.63546		
Attributes of job satisfaction	Below 30 years	61	3.2408	.84389	1.472	0.226
	31 - 40 years	31	3.2952	.50959		
	41 - 50 years	12	3.3742	1.02470		
	Above 50 years	12	3.7492	.67924		
	Total	116	3.3217	.77903		

Interpretation:

The above table shows about the relationship between age and dimensions related to work life balance.

In analyzing the relationship between age and work interference with personal life were the level of significance is at 0.001 which is lesser than 0.05. It shows that there is a significant relationship between age and work interference with personal life. It reveals that the respondents above the age group of 50 have highest impact towards work interference with personal life (3.33) and there in no need of taking action towards the factor as the respondents are satisfied towards work interference with personal life as a whole.

In analyzing the relationship between age and personal life interference with work the level of significance is at 0.113 which is greater than 0.05. It shows that there is no significant relationship between age and personal life interference with work.

In analyzing the relationship between age and work personal life enhancement the level of significance is at 0.013 which is lesser than 0.05. It shows that there is a significant relationship between age and work personal life enhancement. It reveals that the respondents above the age group of 50 have highest impact towards work personal life enhancement (3.35) and it is mandatory to action towards the factor as the respondents feel that there is no work/personal life enhancement.

In analyzing the relationship between age and level of acceptance on work life balance the level of significance is at 0.011 which is lesser than 0.05. It shows that there is a significant relationship between age and level of acceptance on work life balance. It reveals that the respondents above the age group of 50 have highest impact towards level of acceptance on work life balance (3.36) and it is mandatory to action towards the factor as the respondents feel negative towards work life balance.

In analyzing the relationship between age and job satisfaction the level of significance is at 0.500 which is greater than 0.05. It shows that there is no significant relationship between age and job satisfaction.

In analyzing the relationship between age and attributes of job satisfaction the level of significance is at 0.226 which is greater than 0.05. It shows that there is no significant relationship between age and attributes of job satisfaction.

Findings:

- Maximum of the respondents are from the age group of below 30 years.
- Most of the respondents are from nuclear family.
- Maximum of the respondents are post graduates in our survey.
- Most of the respondents are post graduates in our survey.
- Maximum of the respondents are earning from 20001 to 30000.
- Most of the respondents agree about juggle work and non-work.
- Maximum of the respondents are neutral about amount of time for non-work activities.
- Most of the respondents agree about energy for work.
- Maximum of the respondents are neutral about effectiveness at work.

There is a relationship between age and Level of acceptance towards difficulty in personal life because of job, Level of acceptance towards not having tie for relaxation with their partner, Level of acceptance towards working late at weekends to deal with paperwork without interruptions, Level of acceptance towards lack of control over their work, Level of acceptance towards harassment, Level of acceptance towards inadequate pay, Level of acceptance towards conflicting job demands and Level of acceptance towards poor computer workstation design, Monitoring

Suggestions:

The companies should take care of employees work load to balance the work life. Organization should consider every individual is unique and precious and should give time for their own personal needs. Increment should be given to the employees for balancing their work life. The organization should increase work life balance programs to reduce company work conflict.

Human resources policies that can be used to increase work-life balance include implementing time off in lieu of overtime pay arrangements, providing a limited number of days of paid leave per year for child care, elder care or personal problems, or having policies around weekend and evening use of laptops and BlackBerrys.

Conclusion:

The conclusion is that the companies should take care of employees work load to balance the work life. Organization should consider every individual is unique and precious and should give time for their own personal needs. Increment should be given to the employees for balancing their work life. The organization should increase work life balance programs to reduce company work conflict.

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